

INAOE

Long-Term Survival of Dust Grains Produced After Stellar Eruptions

by

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Abstract

Massive stars experience periods of intense instability in their late stages of evolution, just before their final core-collapse. These periods are characterized by presenting very high mass loss rates during some years or decades, known as stellar outbursts. When these outbursts occur, copious amounts of dust are formed from the erupted mass, which can contribute to the enrichment of the interstellar medium with dust. However, the survival of these dust grains is threatened by the powerful shock waves driven by the eventual explosion of the progenitor star as a supernova. Therefore, in this work, hydrodynamic modeling techniques are used to investigate the effects of the supernova explosion on the recently created dust grains, in order to determine whether complete or partial dust destruction occurs.

Resumen

Las estrellas masivas experimentan períodos de intensa inestabilidad en sus etapas tardías de evolución, justo antes del colapso final de su núcleo. Estos períodos se caracterizan por presentar tasas de pérdida de masa muy altas durante algunos años o décadas, conocidos como erupciones estelares. Cuando ocurren estas erupciones, se forman grandes cantidades de polvo a partir de la masa eyectada, lo cual puede contribuir al enriquecimiento del medio interestelar con polvo. Sin embargo, la supervivencia de estos granos de polvo se ve amenazada por las poderosas ondas de choque generadas si la estrella progenitora explota como supernova. Por lo tanto, en este trabajo, se utilizan técnicas de modelado hidrodinámico para investigar los efectos de la explosión de supernova sobre los granos de polvo recién creados, con el fin de determinar si se produce una destrucción completa o parcial de este polvo.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

During the main sequence phase, stars produce energy by burning hydrogen into helium in their cores. The dominant reaction chain for massive stars is the CNO cycle, in which four protons fuse into a helium nucleus, involving carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen as catalysts (Clayton 1968). The main sequence (MS) stage accounts for about 90 percent of a star's lifetime and ends upon the exhaustion of the hydrogen in the core. During the MS, massive stars have convective cores and radiative envelopes. Later, the star undergoes a contraction until the hydrogen burning is ignited in a shell around the helium core, leading to the expansion and cooling of the star (Kippenhahn et al. 2013).

The subsequent evolution after the MS will depend mainly on three factors: the star's initial mass, chemical composition, and stellar rotation (de Boer & Seggewiss, 2008). The stellar mass is regarded as the dominant parameter that determines the total lifespan of a star. Indeed, stars with masses less than eight solar masses will finish their lives with degenerate cores, expelling their outer layers to become white dwarfs. In contrast, stars with a mass greater than eight solar masses can prevent the carbon/oxygen core from degenerating. They continue fusing heavier elements until an iron core forms, and since it can no longer produce energy through fusion, the core collapses (de Boer & Seggewiss, 2008; Kippenhahn et al., 2013). In many cases, the core collapse leads to a supernova explosion, while some massive stars may collapse to form a compact stellar remnant (a black hole) without a supernova explosion (e.g. Sukhbold et al., 2016; Adams et al., 2017).

The main effects of axial rotation on the stellar properties due to the centrifugal

force, are structural changes such as chemical mixing, anisotropic stellar winds and magnetic fields, which are important in rotating stars (e.g. Maeder & Meynet, 2000; Meynet et al., 2006).

On the other hand, chemical composition is another fundamental parameter in stellar evolution, especially due to its close relationship with mass loss. This connection is driven by the metal content of the star, where higher metal content leads to a stronger stellar wind. The mechanism behind the stellar wind is based on the absorption and scattering of photons during atomic transitions, which in turn imparts momentum to the star's outer layers. Consequently, the higher the abundance of metals, the greater the mass loss rate (Lamers & Cassinelli 1999, Kudritzki & Puls 2000, Puls et al. 2008). Mass loss through stellar winds plays an important role in the evolution of massive stars because it ultimately determines the star's final mass before it undergoes its core-collapse. As the star loses mass, it also impacts the rate at which it burns fuel in its core. Additionally, the stellar wind carries away mass and, with it, a substantial amount of angular momentum, effectively removing almost all of the star's initial angular momentum (Maeder & Meynet, 2000).

Figure 1.1: Eta Carinae observed by the Hubble Space Telescope. Credits: NASA, ESA, N. Smith (University of Arizona) and J. Morse (BoldlyGo Institute).

In addition to the impact of stellar winds, massive stars can also lose mass during eruptive processes, which tend to occur when the star becomes unstable by reaching a critical rotational speed, called the Eddington limit (e.g. Humphreys & Davidson 1994). Indeed, when the Eddington limit is reached, the radiation forces at the surface overcome gravity causing a much larger mass loss. These eruptions can prevail for months or years and give rise to the formation of circumstellar nebulae (e.g. Smith, 2011; Davidson, 2020).

Some of the most luminous stars have violent and episodic events of mass loss with $\dot{M} \gtrsim 10^{-3} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ during the outbursts, whose causes are still not very well understood. These hot evolved stars are known as luminous blue variables (LBV), and their instability may explain the appearance of the upper HR diagram (Humphreys & Davidson 1994, Weis & Bomans 2020).

LBV can undergo much more energetic events (giant eruptions) in which the brightness spontaneously increases by several magnitudes. The best known of such events in our Galaxy is the Great Eruption of η Carinae (η Car) around 1843, when its visual magnitude increased to -1 mag for a short period of time before decreasing by 7 magnitudes in just a few years (Davidson & Humphreys 1997). η Car is a binary system with two very massive components, with masses of $60 M_{\odot}$ and $30 M_{\odot}$, respectively (Madura et al. 2012). The nebula has a bipolar shape and is made up of at least three sections: The Homunculus, first identified by Gaviola (1950), The Little Homunculus, which lies within the Homunculus, and the outer ejecta, which surrounds the Homunculus (see figure 1.1).

The Great Eruption resulted in the ejection of a massive amount of material. The high density, low temperature, and abundance of refractory elements provided favorable conditions for the formation of dust particles from the erupted gas. Hence, in the cool and dense regions of the expanding shell created by the eruption, dust grains were formed. In fact, it has been estimated that up to $0.4 M_{\odot}$ of dust were produced after the eruption (Gall & Hjorth 2018a).

However, there is still the question about what will happen to such dust if the star finally explodes as a supernova. The intense radiation field and shocks in these environments can also lead to the destruction or disruption of dust grains through different processes, which are discussed in the following section.

1.1 Interstellar dust

Interstellar dust is an important component of the interstellar medium (ISM). It is responsible for different astrophysical processes that reflect in the dynamics and thermodynamics of galaxies, such as the gas behavior and star formation (Draine 2003a, Tielens 2005). The most obvious manifestation of dust is given by its ability to absorb and scatter starlight, with more relevance in UV and optical wavelengths while it is re-radiated in the infrared (Draine 2003b).

One of the first evidences of the existence of dust was presented by William Herschel with the so-called dark nebulae or “holes in the sky”, since he noticed regions in the sky that apparently lacked stars (Herschel 1785). Since then, it was thought that there was something in the interstellar medium that did not let the light of the stars pass through.

Nevertheless, the first observational discovery of dust due to the effects of light extinction was made by Robert Trumpler in 1930, who was studying the relationship between the apparent brightness and the angular diameter of open clusters. A linear dependence between brightness and the square of the diameter was expected; however, Trumpler found that the more distant clusters were fainter than expected: their light was absorbed by interstellar dust (Trumpler 1930). Subsequently, observational techniques enabled the exploration of different wavelength ranges, which allowed a more detailed study of the existence and properties of the interstellar dust.

It has been estimated that less than 1% of the total dust mass of the Galaxy absorbs/scatters about 30 – 50 % of all the starlight emitted in our Galaxy. That is, only a small percentage of the mass is responsible for half of the total luminosity of the galaxy (Xu & Buat, 1995; Kar, 2007). In the ISM of the Milky Way, the composition of dust grains is dominated by carbonaceous, silicates and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), whose sizes vary between 0.001 and 1 μm (Draine, 2003a; Tielens, 2013). Since dust is mixed with the gas and is observed mainly in star-forming environments (molecular clouds), it protects the molecules from photo-destruction caused by penetrating ultraviolet photons, acts as a catalyst for the creation of molecular gas, encloses much of the heavy elements in solid form and allows the formation of

planetary systems (Tielens 2005, Draine 2011).

However, despite its various manifestations, the nature and origin of dust in galaxies remain poorly understood. Several studies have proposed that dust grains form in the dense and cold envelopes of evolved stars through their stellar winds, especially stars in the Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) stage, red supergiants, Wolf Rayet and LBV. Also, it has been well accepted that supernova (SN) explosions are important contributors to dust formation (e.g. Todini & Ferrara 2001, Matsuura et al. 2009, Gall & Hjorth 2018b, Sarangi et al. 2018).

1.1.1 Dust formation and growth

In the environments of stellar envelopes and supernova remnants, typical conditions for dust formation occur as the gas cools down, reaching densities of $\sim 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and temperatures $\lesssim 2000 \text{ K}$.

Dust formation studies have been based on classical nucleation theory and thermodynamics. Basically, dust formation can be described in two steps (e.g. Demyk 2011). The first one is nucleation, in which gas condenses to form stable nuclei. Indeed, this occurs as vapor is supersaturated with respect to the liquid phase when the pressure of the vapor is greater than that of the liquid at a given temperature (Feder et al. 1966). Thus, a vapor in that state of supersaturation allows the formation of solid materials from gas particles. Around 1400-1500 K, main dust formation occurs and involves the condensation of iron, magnesium and silicon (Tielens 2022). The second step is grain growth by accretion or coagulation of gas-phase atoms or molecules on the surface, or by low-energy collisions between grains.

Dust formation sources

AGB Stars

After stars with 1-8 M_{\odot} exhaust the helium in their core, they will continue their evolution in the AGB stage, in which helium and hydrogen are burned in shells around a core of carbon and oxygen (Gall et al., 2011).

The AGB phase is characterized by a rapid mass loss (superwind) phase, which is believed to be due to thermal pulses (typically $\dot{M} = 10^{-4} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) (Zijlstra, 2006;

Gall et al., 2011). Due to their dense and cold wind conditions, AGB stars provide a favorable environment for nucleation.

Generally, AGB stars can either be carbon-rich (C) or oxygen-rich (M). It is in the thermal pulsations phase in which the chemical abundance in the stellar atmosphere can vary due to the dredge-up processes. In particular, the carbon/oxygen (C/O) ratio will change as the star evolves, therefore, two main kinds of dust can be produced depending on the source (e.g. Tielens, 2005; Dwek, 2005):

- i) M stars ($C/O \leq 1$): Carbon combines with oxygen to form CO. Excess oxygen forms silicate dust.
- ii) C stars ($C/O \geq 1$): All the oxygen is used to create CO and the excess carbon condenses as carbonaceous solids and PAHs.

In the case where $C/O \approx 1$ (S stars), the abundance of elements is insufficient to produce dust, hence only a small amount can be formed.

Red Supergiants

The red supergiant (RSG) phase corresponds to the last stage of evolution of moderately massive stars ($10\text{-}30 M_{\odot}$) that burn helium in their core (Cherchneff, 2013). These stars have luminosities ($\sim 10^3 L_{\odot}$), and temperatures (~ 3500 K) similar to those of low-mass AGB stars (Ziurys, 2006). Furthermore, they experience high mass loss rates ($10^{-6} - 10^{-4} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; Cherchneff, 2013) during this phase.

Due to the gas conditions and complex dynamics in the photosphere and in the winds of RSGs, there have been difficulties in understanding and modeling processes that explain dust formation in such environments (Cherchneff, 2013). However, it has been recognized that in some RSGs the dust formation process is similar to that of the AGBs at radii close to the star center, producing mostly silicate dust as in the case of oxygen-rich stars. Furthermore, due to the absence of AGB stars, the dust produced in RSGs plays a very important role in early galaxies, along with type II supernovae, with a dust production rate of $3 \times 10^{-8} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}$ (Massey et al. 2005).

Wolf-Rayet stars

Wolf-Rayet (WR) stars are evolved massive stars characterized by high mass loss rates, strong stellar winds and excessive infrared outflows. Although these stars are not considered major contributors to dust formation, they have been of great interest because their excess infrared emission has been attributed to episodes of dust formation, with WR140 being the first WR star observed to show strong variations indicating the presence and production of dust (Williams et al. 1990).

Understanding the dust formation processes in the carbon-rich WR star environments is challenging because of their typically unfavorable wind conditions. However, observations of WR stars with various spectral types have shed light on the origin of dust in binary systems. In these instances, the companion star is usually an OB star, and the collision of their stellar winds promotes dust nucleation and growth, especially near the periastron passage, underscoring the significance of binarity in this process. (Crowther 2003).

Luminous Blue Variable Stars

This class of stars is commonly attributed to the stages of photometric variability of massive stars, which can experience large eruptions with high rates of mass loss, typically $10^{-5} - 10^{-4} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Humphreys & Davidson 1994). As a consequence of the giant eruptions and the high mass loss rate, dusty nebulae are formed with a strong emission in the infrared.

For many years the origin of the dust present in the envelopes of these stars has been studied, since the processes that allow their formation are still matter of intense investigation. For instance, according to the models of Gail et al. 2005, as the star evolves and expels its outer layers, causing a reduction in the abundance of C and O, the composition of the condensed dust is anticipated to deviate from the standard. This shift may lead to the formation of metallic dust components, including FeSi and Si. More recently, studying our galaxy's most famous LBV, η Car, allowed us to understand the ideal conditions for dust production in these sources. For example, it has been possible to prove that in the shock regions of the colliding binary winds of η Car, dust formation is promoted episodically (Smith 2010). Also, physical conditions during eruptions have been shown to favour condensation and dust growth, in which

temperature and density are consistent for mass loss rates typical of giant eruptions, $\dot{M} > 10^{-2.5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Kochanek 2011).

Supernovae

Massive stars ($M > 8 M_{\odot}$) complete their evolution with a violent core-collapse, and possibly as supernovae, which are powerful explosions that release huge amounts of energy, momentum and enriched material to the surrounding media. Supernovae (SNe), in particular Type II SNe (SNII), are considered to be efficient dust producers. For instance, infrared observations revealed the existence of dust in supernova remnants such as SN1987A and Cas A, with estimates as high as nearly $1 M_{\odot}$ of dust created in the first years following these explosions (e.g. Dunne et al. 2009, Matsuura et al. 2009, 2015).

However, SNe are also regarded as one of the main dust destruction mechanisms. Indeed, when the supernova occurs, it generates a forward (also called leading or blast) shock and a reverse shock. The forward shock sweeps the surrounding ambient gas into a shell, while the reverse shock thermalizes and decelerates the supernova ejecta. As energetic collisions between gas and dust particles are promoted, the latter can be subjected to destruction (e.g. Vink, 2020).

An important fraction of the dust detected in SN1987A and Cas A have not still been processed by the reverse shock, and for this reason one of the main questions currently addressed in the literature is whether or not the dust grains formed within SNe ejecta manage to survive the passage of the reverse shock wave.

More recent theoretical studies carried out through hydrodynamic simulations have found that approximately 30% of the dust mass produced in the SNe ejecta manages to survive despite having been processed by multiple shocks (Martínez-González et al. 2019). Also, it has been shown that small grains ($< 0.1 \mu\text{m}$) are easily destroyed, while sufficiently large grains ($0.25\text{--}0.5 \mu\text{m}$) could survive to eventually be injected to the surrounding ISM (see also Slavin et al., 2020). It has also been possible to demonstrate that the dust content coming from SNe is consistent with the dust masses obtained in galaxies at high redshift and in environments with low metallicities (Martínez-González et al., 2022).

1.1.2 Destruction processes

After their formation and ejection into the interstellar medium (ISM), dust grains can be subject to various processes leading to their destruction or fragmentation. In the 1940s, Van de Hulst proposed an initial concept, suggesting that particles in the ISM could combine on surfaces to create frozen molecules, a theory later referred to as the 'dirty ice' dust model (van de Hulst, 1946). Subsequently, Oort and van de Hulst calculated that the accumulation of grains in the ISM, up to a radius of 100 nanometers (nm) over a time span of 10^8 years, is counterbalanced by the destruction of dust due to cloud-cloud collisions occurring roughly every 10^8 years. This equilibrium implies an estimated lifetime of approximately 50 million years for these dust grains (Oort & van de Hulst, 1946).

The most important dust destruction processes are described below.

Photodesorption

Photodesorption is the process in which atoms or molecules are removed from the grains surface by the absorption of a photon. In particular, the photodesorption caused by high-energy ultraviolet photons on the surface of ice mantles formed in dense media, such as diffuse clouds, is considered an efficient destruction mechanism, since it is capable of quickly destroying the grains, which are very volatile materials (e.g. Barlow 1978; Jones 2004).

Supernova Explosions

Collisions with an atom/ion at high speeds in hot and dense media is regarded as the main dust destruction mechanism, giving rise to the sputtering of the grains where the conversion of matter from the solid phase to the gas phase occurs.

The sputtering process at energies greater than 10 eV commonly occurs in the environments of shock waves produced by SNe, causing the destruction of dust grains due to collisions with the gas (e.g. Jones, 2004; Jones & Nuth, 2011).

As Jones (2004) explains, in a hot gas ($\sim 10^6$ K), the thermal motion of the atoms/ions (mainly H^+) gives rise to the so-called thermal sputtering. At low velocities, where the grains move relative to the gas due to their inertia, the sputtering process is

dominated by He^+ (inertial sputtering).

Although ionic collisions usually lead to dust destruction, especially small grains, radiative cooling plays a relevant role in the dust fate. Efficient heating of small grains by electronic collisions leads them to strongly radiate at near-infrared (NIR) to mid-infrared (MIR) wavelengths. This emission occurs due to the thermal energy absorbed by the grains and stochastically radiated away (Dwek, 1986). That is, radiative cooling from the smaller grains contributes to the overall cooling of the surrounding medium. Consequently, the presence of these grains and their interactions with the gas can strongly influence the gas thermodynamics and allow larger grains to survive (Martínez-González et al. 2018).

Grain-Grain Collisions

Collisions can favour accretion and coagulation by increasing the overall size of the grains; however, collisions at higher velocities result in their fragmentation or disruption. At velocities of around 1 km s^{-1} , shattering of the homogeneous solid particles into smaller fragments occurs. When the speed of the collision is increased to 20 km s^{-1} , vaporization of the grains can occur (Tielens et al. 1994). Nevertheless, vaporization due to grain-grain collisions is less effective than sputtering, with a vaporization rate of less than 1 % (Jones et al. 1996; Jones 2004).

Thermal Sublimation

Direct heating of the grains due to interactions with high energy photons can cause their sublimation when the temperatures exceed their sublimation limit, $T_{sub} = 1500\text{--}1800 \text{ K}$ (Guhathakurta & Draine, 1989). This occurs primarily when the grains are exposed to intense ultraviolet (UV) or X-rays radiation fields.

Rotational Disruption by Radiative Torques

Dust grains with irregular symmetry experience radiative torques (RATs) when exposed to intense radiation fields, which can lead to a centrifugal stress due to the rapid rotation (Hoang et al., 2019). Under certain circumstances, the high rotation velocity may cause that the tensile stress exceeds the maximum tensile strength of

the grains. Thus, in such cases the grains undergo instantaneous fragmentation into smaller grains.

This new destruction method was proposed in order to reproduce the excess NIR-MIR emission from young stellar clusters and the large extinction and polarization observed around Type Ia SNe, young massive star clusters (YMSCs) and kilonovae, as it cannot be explained with the known destruction methods previously described (e.g Hoang et al. 2019, Hoang 2020).

1.2 Cooling processes and shock wave dynamics in the ISM

1.2.1 Radiative cooling

In low density plasmas, the process of collisional excitation of ions leads to radiative cooling. In this process, the atom/ion or molecule gains energy from the kinetic energy of the colliding pair. Subsequently, the excited system releases this acquired energy in the form of a photon, which can then escape. As a result, the gas loses kinetic energy and cools down (Draine, 2011).

At high temperatures ($T > 10^4$ K), ionization of hydrogen generates a significant number of free electrons, causing electronic collisions to dominate the collisional excitation of atoms in low density plasmas. In these conditions, nearly every collisional excitation is subsequently followed by a radiative decay. The latter results in the net cooling of gas as thermal energy is transformed into radiation. Thus, the cooling rate per unit volume (denoted as Q) can be expressed as:

$$Q = n_e n_H \times \Lambda(T, Z). \quad (1.2.1)$$

Here, n_e represents the electron density, n_H is the hydrogen density, and $\Lambda(T, Z)$ is the radiative cooling function, which is a function of the temperature and the elemental abundances relative to hydrogen.

Figure 1.2: Cooling curve as a function of temperature, taken from Schure *et al.* (2009). The plots represents different contributions to the cooling rate by individual elements for solar metallicity. The overall cooling curve (solid black line) results from the summation of these individual contributions.

However, at higher plasma densities, radiative cooling can be suppressed due to collisional deexcitation. In such cases, the radiative cooling function will also depend

Figure 1.3: Cooling curves for different dust grain size distributions taken from Martínez-González et al. (2016). Panel a: the value of a_{min} (minimum grain size), is set to $0.001 \mu\text{m}$ and a_{max} (cut-off value) has different values (0.001 , 0.01 , and $0.5 \mu\text{m}$), represented by dashed, dotted, and dash-dotted lines, respectively. Panel b: a_{max} is set to $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ while a_{min} varies (0.001 , 0.01 , and $0.5 \mu\text{m}$). The calculations assume a dust-to-gas mass ratio of $\mathcal{D} = 10^{-3}$, and the interstellar cooling law for a solar metallicity is represented by a solid curve in both panels.

on the density n_H in addition to temperature and elemental abundances. Plasmas commonly found in the circumstellar regions of massive stars tend to have high temperatures and are predominantly optically thin. As a result, they have a high capacity for efficient cooling (Schure et al., 2009).

The cooling function, also known as the cooling curve, describes the rate at which a gas or plasma cools down by losing thermal energy through various processes, such as radiation, collisional excitation, and recombination. The units of the cooling function are $\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^3$, hence the cooling rate per unit volume has units of $\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-3}$. That is, the greater the system's density, the more effectively the gas can be cooled down. Figure 1.2 shows an example of a cooling curve for solar abundances (Schure et al., 2009). At high temperatures ($> 10^7 \text{K}$), the gas becomes completely ionized, and cooling is primarily dominated by bremsstrahlung, where $\Lambda \propto T^{0.5}$. Between $\sim 10^{4.7}$ and $\sim 10^7 \text{K}$, metals like Mg, Si, and Fe are present, greatly increasing Λ . At temperatures above a few 10^4K , all the hydrogen is ionized, leading to a decrease in its contribution to cooling and a distinctive drop in Λ . Finally, at lower temperatures, the dominant cooling mechanisms involve collisional line excitation of

hydrogen (occurring at $T \sim 10^{4.2}$ K) and collisional line excitation of He (at $T \sim 10^5$ K) (Draine, 2011).

As previously discussed in section 1.1.2, when dust grains are immersed in the gas, they predominantly interact with free electrons, resulting in their efficient heating and subsequent emission in the IR. From taking a look at the dust cooling curves depicted in Fig. 1.3, we observe that at high temperatures, the role of dust-induced cooling becomes increasingly significant. Dust grains exhibit remarkable efficiency in cooling the surrounding gas, contributing to a substantial increase in several orders of magnitude in energy loss. Notably, smaller dust grains experience quicker heating due to their low heat capacities, which scale with volume as $\sim a^3$, further emphasizing their role in the cooling process (Martínez-González et al., 2016).

The substantial impact of dust-induced cooling on gas behavior at these temperatures underscores the importance of implementing this cooling channel in hydrodynamical simulations.

1.2.2 Shock waves

Shock waves are common phenomena in the ISM. They can occur in various astrophysical scenarios, including stellar explosions (novae, kilonovae and SNe), deceleration of fast stellar winds upon encountering the ISM, expanding H II regions, shock transitions in spiral galaxies, and shock waves resulting from collisions between clouds moving supersonically in a star-forming galaxy (Draine, 2011).

Shock waves are commonly defined as the transition surface in which the flow and thermodynamic properties of the plasma/gas change abruptly. They arise when material moves at velocities exceeding the sound speed in the surrounding medium, and it cannot dynamically respond until the upcoming material arrives.

Jump Conditions

The jumps (abrupt changes) in the fluid properties (density, temperature, velocity, and pressure) observed in a shock transition are described by the Rankine-Hugoniot relations, which relate the pre-shock and post-shock state of the fluid.

The changes in a plasma conditions across the shock-transition layer consistently adhere to the mass, momentum, and energy conservation laws. It is useful to adopt a

reference frame that moves with the shock itself and the shock front can be approximated as plane-parallel. Under these considerations, the so-called Rankine-Hugoniot jump conditions can be expressed as (Tielens, 2005; Vink, 2020):

$$\rho_1 v_1 = \rho_2 v_2, \quad (1.2.2)$$

$$P_1 + \rho_1 v_1^2 = P_2 + \rho_2 v_2^2, \quad (1.2.3)$$

$$(P_1 + U_1 + \frac{1}{2}\rho_1 v_1^2) v_1 = (P_2 + U_2 + \frac{1}{2}\rho_2 v_2^2) v_2, \quad (1.2.4)$$

where ρ is the density, P the pressure, and U the internal energy of the gas. The labels 1 and 2 denote the quantities in the unshocked (upstream) and the shocked regions (downstream), respectively. The velocities are measured relative to the shock front. When radiative cooling (or heating) becomes important, the energy exchange with the environment can be accounted for in equation 1.2.4.

Radiative Shocks

As gas passes through a shock wave, it undergoes heating. Typically, heated gases emit radiation, and this radiation leads to the removal of energy from the gas. The temperature behind a shock wave depends on the shock velocity ($T \propto V^2$) and the molecular weight of the gas. In cases of high shock velocities ($> 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), the temperature of the gas after the shock exceeds 10^6 K , and it subsequently undergoes a relatively gradual cooling process (see section 1.2.1).

When radiative cooling becomes important, a runaway process is triggered: pressure balance requires the plasma to compress, but the higher density increases notably the gas cooling. This process decelerates as the plasma cools down to approximately 10^4 K , where the cooling time scale (the time it takes the gas to radiate away its internal energy acquired while passing through the shock wave), becomes longer again due to the diminishing efficiency of radiative cooling (e.g. Dyson & Williams, 1980; Vink, 2020)

Henceforth, the terms *blast wave*, *forward shock*, and *shock wave* will be used interchangeably.

1.3 Aims and outline of the Thesis

The dust produced by a stellar outburst can be affected when the star subsequently explodes as a supernova (SN), due to the enormous amount of energy in the form of a shock wave. The extreme conditions associated with this shock wave can lead to the destruction of the dust grains.

Hence, the main goal of this thesis is to determine if the dust created after the stellar eruption can survive against the eventual SN shock processing.

To achieve this, hydrodynamic simulations have been performed, for the first time, that model the shaping of the interstellar medium due to the progenitor's stellar wind, the occurrence of a giant stellar outburst (spherical or bipolar) that creates a large amount of dust particles, and the subsequent SN explosion.

This thesis is organized as follows: Chapter 2 introduces the physics of stellar winds and stellar eruptions. Chapter 3 describes the models of the stellar eruption and the SN explosion implemented in the simulations. Chapter 4 provides a description of the hydrodynamical setup, the initial conditions and the physical parameters used. Chapter 5 reports the obtained results and Chapter 6 gives the final conclusions and discusses the future work.

Stellar Winds and Eruptions

During their evolution, stars experience fast outflows which inject mechanical energy and momentum into the interstellar medium (ISM), and through which they lose mass. These outflows, known as stellar winds, lead to the formation of bubbles around the star since the winds are ejected into the ISM at supersonic speeds (Draine, 2011). Moreover, massive stars may also undergo significant eruptions during their lifetime. These outbursts are explosive events during which a massive amount of material, including gas and dust, is ejected from the star's surface into space. These stellar eruptions can lead to the creation of more complex structures and contribute to the enrichment of the ISM with heavy elements and dust particles (Kochanek, 2011; Smith, 2014).

This chapter presents a brief introduction to the observed properties and diagnostics of stellar winds. For a more detailed description, see, for example, Lamers & Cassinelli (1999) and Kudritzki & Puls (2000). Furthermore, a preliminary overview of stellar eruptions in massive stars and their significant impact on the ISM is provided.

2.1 Global properties of stellar winds

The most important parameters describing a stellar wind are the mass loss rate \dot{M} , i.e., how much mass the star loses per unit of time, and the wind terminal velocity v_∞ , the velocity of the wind at large distances from the star.

The mass loss rate (\dot{M}) is related to the density (ρ) and velocity (v) for a stationary and spherically symmetric wind as:

$$\dot{M} = 4\pi r^2 \rho(r) v(r). \quad (2.1.1)$$

The wind velocity distribution can be approximated by:

$$v(r) = v_\infty \left(1 - b \frac{R_*}{r}\right)^\beta, \quad b = 1 - \left(\frac{v(R_*)}{v_\infty}\right)^{1/\beta}, \quad (2.1.2)$$

where b and v_∞ are parameters that can be fitted from the observed spectra.

Several models of stellar atmospheres and calculations of radiative transport are required in order to estimate the global parameters of the stellar winds, as they are not directly observable.

P Cygni lines. Ultraviolet P Cygni profiles are important in the determination of stellar wind parameters because they are the most sensitive mass-loss rate diagnostics, and allow determinations of very low values of \dot{M} , typically down to $10^{-10} \text{ M}_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Martins, 2011). These lines originate when a photon in the photosphere is absorbed by an atom causing a photo-excitation followed by a de-excitation. Consequently, the photon will be re-emitted in the almost same frequency as the absorbed one. P Cygni profiles have two components: an absorption component, which is produced by the material that moves towards the observer's line of view, and therefore is blue-shifted, and its corresponding emission component (Kudritzki & Puls, 2000).

If the ionization/excitation fractions and abundances are well known, the mass loss rate can be obtained from the P Cygni profiles. However, if the lines are saturated, the derivation of mass loss rates is highly uncertain and only allows the determination of a lower limit for \dot{M} .

Recombination lines. Unlike the P Cygni lines, the hydrogen recombination lines present simpler ionization corrections, which is why they are used as indicators of mass loss rates. For O-stars, the H_α line is the most widely used diagnostic, as it has the advantage of being optically thin in most of the wind and is not affected by porosity effects. This indicator allows the estimation of mass loss rates greater than $10^{-7} \text{ M}_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Vink, 2022).

Infrared and radio continuum emission. Hot stars show an excess of infrared and radio emission caused by free-free (Bremsstrahlung) emission in their winds. The measure-

ment of this excess of radiation relative to the flux from the stellar photosphere is used as a complementary diagnostic of the wind mass loss rate. Due to the λ^3 dependence on the opacities, the excess flow becomes dominant at longer wavelengths. As the continuum becomes optically thick, the volume of the emitted wind increases with wavelength, thus forming a photosphere where radio emission dominates stellar photospheric emission (Wright & Barlow, 1975). At radio wavelengths, this diagnostic provides a determination of mass loss rates greater than $10^{-6} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

2.2 Radiation-driven winds

The winds from hot luminous stars are driven by the pressure gradient of the radiation emitted by the star. In the star’s atmosphere, where radiation and gas pressure forces overcome gravity, material flows outwards and produces the stellar wind. Line radiation is the most important mechanism for the winds of such hot stars, where the momentum of photons is transferred to the stellar atmosphere through absorption by spectral lines. However, in the case of very massive stars, which tend to expel material through large eruptions, their winds are expected to be driven by continuum radiation, since the high kinetic energy cannot be explained with a line-driven wind (e.g. Owocki et al., 2004; Davidson, 2020; Vink, 2022).

2.3 Giant Eruptions

Massive evolved stars experience episodes of high mass loss in the late stages of their lives, before they become a supernova (SN) or collapse to form a black hole. These powerful giant eruptions are referred to as “supernova impostors”, since some of their observational features appear to be of a true SN. One of the most famous historical events of this type in the Milky Way is the Great eruption of η Carinae (η Car) in the 1840s, that formed its famous bipolar nebula known as the Homunculus (Humphreys & Davidson, 1994; Davidson & Humphreys, 1997). η Car is a luminous binary star system classified as LBV. The binary orbit has an eccentricity of 0.9 and its orbital period is of 2023.7 days (Corcoran et al., 2017). It was until the early 1800 that it was reported to be as a fourth or second magnitude star, but in the next 30 years it

Figure 2.1: Scheme of a SN remnant interacting with a bipolar circumstellar medium (CSM) created by a stellar eruption, subsequent to the ejection of the stellar wind. Panel a) shows the expansion of the SN ejecta and the forward shock at early times after the explosion. Panel b) represents the moment in which the SN begins to interact with the dense shell of the eruption some time later.

showed more variability and reached almost one magnitude (Davidson & Humphreys, 1997). Later, The Great Eruption began in 1837 and continued for several years, reaching its peak brightness in 1843. During this period, η Car underwent a dramatic increase in luminosity, becoming the second brightest object in the sky (Humphreys et al., 1999).

Another of the best known historical giant eruptions in the Galaxy is P Cygni, that occurred around 1600 (Israelian & de Groot, 1999).

2.3.1 LBVs and Core-collapse Supernovae

Core-collapse Supernovae (CCSNe) are explosive events that occur at the end of a star which has a zero-age main-sequence mass $\geq 8 M_{\odot}$. The core collapses under its own gravity and triggers a powerful explosion, releasing an enormous amount of energy ($\sim 10^{51}$ erg).

On the other hand, LBVs are stars going through an unstable phase of their evolution,

and their mass loss can be very high, leading to the ejection of significant amounts of material into the surrounding medium. This mass loss creates a dense circumstellar medium (CSM) around the star (Smith, 2011). Some CCSNe are thought to be the result of LBVs undergoing a final explosive event, particularly Type IIn SNe, in which the interaction between the ejected material and the CSM can greatly influence the resulting SN (Dwarkadas, 2011). This category of SNe, which shows evidence of shock interaction with a pre-existing CSM, is commonly known as interacting SNe (Smith & Andrews, 2020).

Interacting SNe in a non-spherical CSM are intriguing events that occur when a SN explosion interacts with an asymmetric environment around the progenitor star. The presence of non-spherical CSM structures, such as disks or bipolar outflows, is common around evolved massive stars. This asymmetry can significantly impact the appearance and interpretation of observed signatures of CSM interaction (Smith, 2017; Smith & Andrews, 2020), as is the case of the supernova SN2014C, which showed intense X-ray emission as a result of the SN-CSM interaction, over a timescale of several years (Brethauer et al., 2022).

Figure 2.1 shows the basic structure seen in this scenario.

There are other several notable examples where LBVs have been proposed as the progenitors of CCSNe, for instance, the supernovae SN 2001ig and SN2003bg (Kotak & Vink, 2006), SN 2005gj (Trundle et al., 2008), SN2005gl (Gal-Yam et al., 2007) and SN 2017hcc (Kumar et al., 2019; Smith & Andrews, 2020). These events showed evidence of strong interaction with the CSM, consistent with the expected LBV mass loss.

Summary

This chapter has introduced basic concepts related to stellar winds and their global properties, as well as the phenomenon of stellar eruptions, often observed in massive evolved stars like LBVs. One notable example is the η Carinae's Great Eruption in the 1840s, which occurred during its LBV phase. These massive stars, with their high mass loss rates, can create a dense CSM. As these massive stars evolve, they may eventually face their fate as CCSNe, releasing an enormous amount of energy and momentum

into their surroundings. Moreover, this chapter explores the intriguing phenomenon of interacting SNe in non-spherical CSM environments. This dynamic interplay between massive stars, their ejected materials, and the resulting SNe highlights the complex processes occurring in the late stages of stellar evolution.

Stellar Eruptions and Supernovae Modelling

Observational studies of the Homunculus nebula have revealed details about its density structure and morphology, which exhibits a dense shell-like structure around the central binary system (Steffen et al., 2014 and references therein). These observations provide valuable information about the density distribution in the ejecta of η Car, thus contributing to our understanding of the physics and properties of such powerful stellar giant eruptions.

This chapter presents the adopted initial density and velocity distribution functions of both stellar eruptions and supernova (SN) ejecta, which for a variety of SN types is described by power-law models (e.g. Chevalier, 1986; Truelove & McKee, 1999; Tang & Chevalier, 2017), as discussed in the following section.

3.1 Initial conditions for the SN explosions

Although only two parameters, namely the ambient gas density and energy, are required to describe the evolution of a SN remnant in the classic Sedov-Taylor stage (e.g. Ostriker & McKee, 1988), in order to model their evolution from the early, ejecta-dominated stage, it is necessary to consider as input parameters the total deposited energy $E_{k,SN}$, the maximum ejecta expansion velocity $v_{ej,SN}$ and the total ejected mass $M_{ej,SN}$. Furthermore, an index ω is usually introduced to describe the gas distribution with power-law functions.

Figure 3.1: SN ejecta density distribution as a function of the normalized radius $w = r/R_{\text{ej,SN}}$ for three different cases of the core radius, as indicated by the inset.

Following Truelove & McKee (1999) (hereafter TM99), and Tang & Chevalier (2017), it is assumed that the supernova ejecta density and velocity distributions are:

$$\rho_{\text{ej,SN}}(r) = \frac{M_{\text{ej,SN}}}{R_{\text{ej,SN}}^3} f_{\text{SN}} \left(\frac{r}{R_{\text{ej,SN}}} \right), \quad (3.1.1)$$

$$v(r, t) = \begin{cases} r/t & \text{if } r \leq R_{\text{ej,SN}}, \\ 0 & \text{if } r > R_{\text{ej,SN}}, \end{cases} \quad (3.1.2)$$

where $M_{\text{ej,SN}}$ and $v_{\text{ej,SN}}$ are the ejecta mass and maximum expansion velocity, $R_{\text{ej,SN}} = v_{\text{ej,SN}}t$ is the initial ejecta radius and $f_{\text{SN}}(r/R_{\text{ej,SN}})$ is a structure function:

$$f_{\text{SN}}(w_{\text{SN}}) = \begin{cases} f_{0,\text{SN}} & \text{if } 0 \leq w_{\text{SN}} \leq w_{\text{core,SN}}, \\ f_{\omega,\text{SN}} w_{\text{SN}}^{-\omega} & \text{if } w_{\text{core,SN}} \leq w \leq 1, \end{cases} \quad (3.1.3)$$

where $w_{\text{SN}} = r/R_{\text{ej,SN}}$ and $w_{\text{core,SN}} = R_{\text{core,SN}}/R_{\text{ej,SN}}$ are normalized radii, and ω is the power-law index of the SN ejecta.

Equation 3.1.3 is a piece-wise function, with a constant density core up to the radius $R_{\text{core,SN}}$ and an outer power-law envelope, which is required to obtain a finite mass for cases with $\omega > 3$.

We notice that by continuity and mass normalization (TM99):

$$f_{\omega,\text{SN}} = \frac{3}{4\pi} \left[\frac{1 - \omega/3}{1 - (\omega/3)w_{\text{core,SN}}^{3-\omega}} \right]. \quad (3.1.4)$$

Furthermore, the SN input parameters $E_{\text{k,SN}}$, $v_{\text{ej,SN}}$ and $M_{\text{ej,SN}}$ are not independent; instead, they are related by the normalization of the total energy:

$$\frac{E_{\text{k,SN}}}{(1/2)M_{\text{ej,SN}} v_{\text{ej,SN}}^2} = \alpha, \quad (3.1.5)$$

with

$$\alpha = \frac{3 - \omega}{5 - \omega} \left[\frac{w_{\text{core,SN}}^{\omega-5} - \omega/5}{w_{\text{core,SN}}^{\omega-3} - \omega/3} \right] w_{\text{core,SN}}^2. \quad (3.1.6)$$

Hence, by combining equations 3.1.5 and 3.1.6, the maximum expansion velocity of the ejecta is given by:

$$v_{\text{ej,SN}} = \left[2w_{\text{core,SN}}^{-2} \left(\frac{5 - \omega}{3 - \omega} \right) \left(\frac{w_{\text{core,SN}}^{\omega-3} - \omega/3}{w_{\text{core,SN}}^{\omega-5} - \omega/5} \right) \frac{E_{\text{k,SN}}}{M_{\text{ej,SN}}} \right]^{1/2}. \quad (3.1.7)$$

3.2 Initial conditions for the stellar eruptions

Similar to a SN explosion, the deposited kinetic energy $E_{\text{k,E}}$, the ejecta maximum expansion velocity $v_{\text{ej,E}}$, and the total mass of ejected material $M_{\text{ej,E}}$ are considered in order to describe the evolution of an expanding bipolar shell, such as the Homunculus. The value of these parameters have to be selected according to the observed properties of the studied nebula.

Here an adapted and novel version of the TM99 approach (see also Tang & Chevalier, 2017) is implemented, which takes into account that the eruption ejecta density,

Figure 3.2: Same as Fig. 3.1 but for the case of a stellar eruption.

increases as one moves away from the center (see figure 3.2). Thus, the density profile of the eruption can be described by:

$$\rho_{\text{ej},E}(r) = \frac{M_{\text{ej},E}}{R_{\text{ej},E}^3} f_E(w_E), \quad (3.2.1)$$

where $R_{\text{ej},E} = v_{\text{ej},E}t$ is the ejecta radius and $f_E(w_E)$ is the structure function, which is given by the following power-law profile:

$$f_E(w_E) = \begin{cases} f_{\omega,E}(1 - w_E)^{-\omega}, & \text{if } 0 \leq w_E \leq w_{\text{core},E}, \\ f_{0,E} & \text{if } w_{\text{core},E} \leq w_E \leq 1, \end{cases} \quad (3.2.2)$$

where

$$w_E = \frac{r_E}{R_{\text{ej},E}}, \quad w_{\text{core},E} = \frac{R_{\text{core},E}}{R_{\text{ej},E}}, \quad (3.2.3)$$

$$f_{\omega,E} = \frac{1}{4\pi\lambda_{f_E}}, \quad (3.2.4)$$

and

$$\lambda_{f_E} = \frac{16}{3} + \frac{2}{3}(1 - w_{\text{core,E}})^{-1.5}(12w_{\text{core,E}} - 3w_{\text{core,E}}^2 - 8) + \frac{1}{3}(1 - w_{\text{core,E}})^{-2.5}(1 - w_{\text{core,E}}^3). \quad (3.2.5)$$

The radial velocity is then given by:

$$v_{\text{ej,E}} = \left[\left(\frac{2E_{k,E}}{M_{\text{ej,E}}} \right) \frac{1}{f_{\omega,E} \lambda_{v,E} + \frac{f_{0,E}}{5}(1 - w_{\text{core,E}})^{0.5}} \right]^{1/2}, \quad (3.2.6)$$

where

$$\lambda_{v,E} = \frac{256}{15} + \frac{2}{3}(1 - w_{\text{core,E}})^{-1.5} - 8(1 - w_{\text{core,E}})^{-0.5} - 12(1 - w_{\text{core,E}})^{0.5} + \frac{8}{3}(1 - w_{\text{core,E}})^{1.5} - \frac{2}{5}(1 - w_{\text{core,E}})^{2.5}. \quad (3.2.7)$$

Summary

The initial density and velocity distribution functions for both stellar eruptions and SN ejecta were discussed employing power-law models. Input parameters such as total energy, maximum expansion velocity, total ejected mass, and a gas distribution index are considered. In the case of stellar eruptions, I proposed an adapted version of TM99 and Tang & Chevalier (2017) approach to describe the evolving bipolar shell, which takes into account the increase of the ejecta density with radii, consistent with the observational data of the Homunculus.

Hydrodynamical Setup

A set of 3-D hydrodynamical simulations have been carried out using the adaptive-mesh refinement (AMR) code FLASH (Fryxell et al., 2000). The code implements the Piece-wise Parabolic Method (PPM) to solve the hydrodynamic equations (Colella & Woodward, 1984), which relies on numerical techniques based on conservation laws, enabling us to predict and reconstruct the fluid properties over time. The package PARAMESH (MacNeice et al., 1999) is used for implementing the AMR grid, that employs a block-structured adaptive mesh refinement scheme. For this work, I implemented novel modifications to the currently working FLASH modules with the aim of studying the evolution of dust particles in bipolar eruptions, as described below.

4.1 Simulation scheme and initial conditions

For the purposes of this work, a series of simulations are performed where a spherical stellar wind initializes the calculations. Later, a stellar eruption is simulated considering different cases with spherical and bipolar geometry. Such eruption produces a certain amount of dust which is injected into the computational domain. Finally, the simulations take into account the effects of a spherical supernova (SN) explosion that interacts with the pre-existing circumstellar medium (CSM) created by the eruption and the stellar wind. The implementation of the stellar wind, the eruption and the SN involves a series of modules and subroutines developed for the FLASH code.

The simulation scheme, therefore, includes the calculation of a time-dependent stellar wind using the WIND module (Wünsch et al., 2017), which also allows the injection of the stellar eruption, and the SN explosion. Additionally, the simulation includes

gas cooling as described by Schure et al. (2009) and radiative cooling resulting from gas-grain collisions, using the CINDER module (Cooling INduced by Dust & Erosion Rates, Martínez-González et al. 2018, 2019, 2022).

4.1.1 Dust Implementation

The injection and destruction of dust in the simulations was carried out with the CINDER module, that also allows to calculate, on-the-fly, the rate of the thermal sputtering within specific grid cells. CINDER incorporates an initial grain size distribution with 10 bins logarithmically spaced, and the dust is traced by means of the dust-to-gas mass ratio as an advecting mass scalar. The grain sizes follow a log-normal distribution of the form $\sim a^{-1} \exp\{-0.5[\ln(a/a_0)/\sigma]^2\}$, where $a_0 = 0.1$, $\sigma = 0.7$, and $a_{min} = 0.005 \mu\text{m}$, $a_{max} = 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ are the lower and upper limits of the grain size, respectively (Martínez-González et al., 2019).

The representative grain sizes for each bin (equidistant in the logarithmic scale) are then defined by

$$a_m^{(i)} = \sqrt{a_{min}^{(i)} a_{max}^{(i)}}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq N_{bins}, \quad (4.1.1)$$

where $a_{min}^{(i)}$ and $a_{max}^{(i)}$ are the lower and upper limits of the respective bin, which are given by

$$a_{min}^{(i)} = a_{min} \times 10^{(i-1)\delta a/N_{bins}}, \quad (4.1.2)$$

and

$$a_{max}^{(i)} = a_{min} \times 10^{i\delta a/N_{bins}}. \quad (4.1.3)$$

In the above equations, N_{bins} is the total number of grain size bins and δa is equal to $\log a_{max} - \log a_{min}$.

Assuming that each grain has a mass $m_{gr}(a) = 4\pi\rho_{gr}a^3/3$, thus the fraction of dust mass in the i th size bin is calculated via

$$f_{M_d}^{(i)} = \frac{\int_{a_{min}^{(i)}}^{a_{max}^{(i)}} a^2 \exp\{-0.5[\ln(a/a_0)/\sigma]^2\} da}{\int_{a_{min}}^{a_{max}} a^2 \exp\{-0.5[\ln(a/a_0)/\sigma]^2\} da}. \quad (4.1.4)$$

When grains are exposed to a plasma at temperatures $\geq 10^6$ K, thermal sputtering occurs due to frequent ionic collisions, causing mass loss from the grain surfaces. After a small time, Δt , the dust-to-gas mass ratio for each size bin, $\mathcal{D}^{(i)}$, decreases as

$$\mathcal{D}^{(i)}(t + \Delta t) = \mathcal{D}^{(i)}(t) \left(1 - \frac{3|\dot{a}|\Delta t}{a_m^{(i)}} \right), \quad (4.1.5)$$

where \dot{a} is the rate of decrease in the grain size, and is given by (Tsai & Mathews, 1995)

$$\dot{a} = -1.4nh \left[\left(\frac{10^6 \text{ K}}{T} \right)^{2.5} + 1 \right]^{-1}. \quad (4.1.6)$$

The above equation depends on the gas number density, n , and the gas temperature, T . Additionally, h is a constant equal to $3.2 \times 10^{-18} \text{ cm}^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

4.1.2 Stellar Wind Insertion

An isotropic stellar wind (which serves as a filling medium) is inserted according to the implementation of Wünsch et al. (2008), in which the wind is inserted into a small sphere with radius R_v and the gas density and velocity around the source are set as:

$$\rho(r) = \frac{\dot{M}_W}{4\pi v_\infty r^2}, \quad v(r) = v_\infty r/R_v, \quad (4.1.7)$$

where \dot{M}_W is the time-dependent mass loss rate and r is the distance from the center. The radius R_v is taken as small as possible such that the wind is approximately spherical.

The wind temperature, T_{wind} , is set to 10^4 K, as proposed in Martínez-González et al. (2019). A mass loss rate $\dot{m} = 10^{-3} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$, and a terminal velocity $v = 250 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ is adopted following González et al. (2022).

The calculations assume solar metallicity ($Z = Z_\odot$), consistent with previous works of η Car (Madura et al.. 2012, 2013).

The stellar wind is let to evolve until it extends beyond the boundaries of the computational domain.

Figure 4.1: The bipolar shape obtained according to equation 4.1.8 is plotted in the xz plane (in dimensionless coordinates) for different values of α and β . In panel a) $\beta = 0.3$, and α takes the values 0.7, 0.8 and 0.9 (solid, dashed, and dotted lines, respectively). In panel b) $\alpha = 0.85$ and β takes the values 0.1, 0.5 and 1.5 (solid, dashed, and dotted lines, respectively).

4.1.3 Stellar Eruption and SN Insertion

In order to insert both the stellar eruption and the SN explosion, the analysis described in chapter 3 was implemented in the FLASH code.

Considering that the mass expelled during the Great Eruption is estimated to be within the range of 12-40 M_{\odot} (Gomez et al., 2010; Gull et al., 2012), this study adopts an average ejecta mass of 25 M_{\odot} . Consequently, with a gas-to-dust ratio ~ 100 (Smith & Ferland, 2007), the ejected dust mass from the eruption is assumed to be 0.25 M_{\odot} . Furthermore, we assume that the kinetic energy of the eruptions are 10^{50} erg (Smith et al., 2018) in all cases.

For the purpose of describing the bipolar morphology of the CSM created by the eruption, it is assumed a latitude-dependent expansion velocity, similar to that proposed in Frank et al. (1995), which has been modified in order to suit a three-dimensional model. That is,

$$v_E = v_{ej,E} F_{\varphi}, \quad F_{\varphi} = 1 - \alpha \left(\frac{1 - e^{-2\beta \sin^2 \varphi}}{1 - e^{-2\beta}} \right), \quad (4.1.8)$$

where φ is the azimuth angle, α controls the pole-to-equator velocity contrast, and β controls the shape of the wind (see figure 4.1).

The values of α and β (0.78 and 0.3, respectively) have been adopted due to their fit with the observational features of the Homunculus (González et al., 2004).

Due to this modification in the expansion velocity, and therefore in the geometry of the ejected mass, a normalization of the kinetic energy $E_{k,E}$ must be taken into account to ensure consistency with the given density profile.

4.1.4 Initial Conditions

Three distinct scenarios were explored based on the shape of the CSM created by the eruption and the time elapsed before the SN explosion. By comparing the characteristics of these scenarios, we can analyze the impact of these parameters on the fate of the dust grains produced after the stellar eruption upon shock-processing.

For the first and second scenarios, it is considered that the SN explosion occurs 200 years after the beginning of the stellar eruption (which is roughly the time elapsed from the Great Eruption of η Car to the present day). These two scenarios also consider an spherically symmetric CSM (case S_{200}), and a bipolar shaped CSM (case B_{200}), respectively. In certain instances, the eruption may occur just a few years prior to the supernova explosion, as exemplified by the interacting supernova SN 2017hcc, with an estimated evolution time range of 6-12 years according to Smith & Andrews (2020). Therefore, in the third scenario (B_{10}), a bipolar CSM experiences a 10-year evolution before the supernova explosion. Table 4.1 lists the input parameters used for the simulations.

The simulations take place in a cubic computational domain where the origin of the Cartesian coordinate system lies at the center. A minimum refinement level of 5 and maximum of 7 are considered¹, obtaining a minimum and maximum spatial resolution of 3094 AU (1.5×10^{-2} pc) and 804 AU (3.9×10^{-3} pc), respectively, for case S_{200} . For case B_{200} , the corresponding resolutions are 1611 AU (7.8×10^{-3} pc) and 402 AU (1.9×10^{-3} pc). While in case B_{10} , the minimum and maximum resolutions are 128 AU (6.2×10^{-4} pc) and 33 AU (1.6×10^{-4} pc), respectively. External boundary

¹For a case with fixed cell-size, a refinement level 7 corresponds to $(512)^3$ cells and a refinement level 5 to $(128)^3$ cells.

Wind				
	v [km s ⁻¹]	\dot{m} [M_{\odot} yr ⁻¹]	T_{wind} [K]	Δt_0 [yr]
<i>Case S₂₀₀</i>	250	10 ⁻³	10 ⁴	5000
<i>Case B₂₀₀</i>	250	10 ⁻³	10 ⁴	2600
<i>Case B₁₀</i>	250	10 ⁻³	10 ⁴	170
Eruption				
	$E_{0,k}$ [erg]	M_{ej} [M_{\odot}]	M_{dust} [M_{\odot}]	Δt_1 [yr]
<i>Case S₂₀₀</i>	10 ⁵⁰	25	0.25	200
<i>Case B₂₀₀</i>	10 ⁵⁰	25	0.25	200
<i>Case B₁₀</i>	10 ⁵⁰	25	0.25	10
Supernova				
	$E_{0,k}$ [erg]	M_{ej} [M_{\odot}]	M_{dust} [M_{\odot}]	Δt_2 [yr]
<i>Case S₂₀₀</i>	10 ⁵¹	10	-	250
<i>Case B₂₀₀</i>	10 ⁵¹	10	-	115
<i>Case B₁₀</i>	10 ⁵¹	10	-	12

Table 4.1: Input parameters. $E_{0,k}$ is the kinetic energy, M_{ej} is the mass of the ejected gas, M_{dust} is the dust mass injected, and Δt_0 , Δt_1 , and Δt_2 are the wind, eruption and SN simulation times, respectively. For the SN explosion, no dust injection is considered.

conditions are set to outflow, therefore the gas can leave the computational domain.

The simulations in this work were performed using resources provided by *Laboratorio Nacional de Supercómputo del Sureste de México* (LNS), through the project 202201018C titled *Huellas Observacionales y Enriquecimiento del Medio Interestelar Violento*.

This chapter presents the results of the 3-D simulations carried out with the FLASH hydrodynamical code. The output format of FLASH in these simulations is available in Hierarchical Data Format (HDF5), which are post-processed through the use of Python scripts.

First, I discuss slices in the x - z plane at four representative times before and after the supernova (SN) explosion. For each case, plots of the gas density (log scale), temperature (log scale) and dust number density (log scale) are presented (Figs. 5.1, 5.2, and 5.4). Then, in Figs. 5.3 and 5.5 the evolution of the dust mass and kinetic energy after the SN explosion are presented.

Cases S_{200} and B_{200} – 200-year eruption-SN delay

One can start the analysis of cases S_{200} and B_{200} , each characterized by a distinct geometry of the circumstellar medium (CSM) created by the eruption: one exhibiting a spherical shape and the other one displaying a bipolar configuration. These scenarios are allowed to evolve for 200 years before the SN explosion occurs. The results of the simulations show that the erupted material piles-up creating a dense shell of $\sim 10^{4.5}$ cm^{-3} for case S_{200} and of $\sim 10^6$ cm^{-3} for case B_{200} , as it can be observed in the density plots in Figures 5.1-5.2.

In the case S_{200} , the interaction of the SN forward shock with the shell begins approximately at $t = 170$ years post-explosion. As the SN shock wave propagates, dust destruction occurs radially from the center, as seen in the bottom row of Figure 5.1. Figure 5.3 shows the evolution of the kinetic energy and the dust mass fraction post-

Figure 5.1: The evolutionary stages of the SN remnant within the erupted CSM for case S_{200} are depicted in four columns, exhibiting snapshots at 0, 40, 170, and 250 years after the SN explosion, respectively. From top to bottom, each row displays, in log scale, the gas density n , the temperature T , and the dust number density ρ_d .

explosion. In case S_{200} , a gradual decrease in the kinetic energy is seen due to the action of radiative cooling. However, it is when the forward shock of the SN collides with the CSM shell that this reduction in kinetic energy becomes significantly pronounced.

As the SN forward shock sweeps through the circumstellar material, a gradual reduction in the dust mass can be observed over a span of approximately 150 years. Nevertheless, the dust mass undergoes a sudden and substantial decline when the SN-CSM shell collision occurs, specifically between $t = 170$ and $t = 180$ years, as depicted in panel *a* of Figure 5.3. These results imply that after 250 years post-explosion, around 75 % of the dust mass ($\sim 0.18 M_{\odot}$) produced in the eruption is destroyed.

Figure 5.2: Same as Figure 5.1 but for case B_{200} , with snapshots at 0, 20, 75 and 115 years after the SN explosion.

The SN remnant evolution in case B_{200} , where the CSM has a bipolar geometry, arises somewhat differently than for the spherical case. After 20 years post-explosion, the SN forward shock reaches the equatorial zone of the shell, where the density is mainly concentrated. As the SN forward shock progresses within the CSM, it becomes increasingly apparent that the SN remnant undergoes deformation, reaching a configuration that closely resembles the bipolar shape of the CSM, as depicted in Figure 5.2. This indicates that, due to the high equatorial densities, the supernova remnant cannot expand freely in such a way that it can eventually disrupt the shell.

At $t = 75$ years, the SN forward shock starts to interact with the shell poles.

Unlike the case S_{200} , in case B_{200} the kinetic energy (dashed blue curve in panel b of Figure 5.3) decays significantly more drastically, due to the proximity of the interaction of the forward shock with the shell's equator (at about $t = 20$ years post-explosion).

Between $t = 50$ and $t = 115$ years, there is a noticeable increase in the kinetic energy, which may be due to the density gradient created by the initial stellar wind. As a result of the SN shock wave encountering this density gradient, it is accelerated (e.g.

Figure 5.3: Panel a shows the evolution of the dust mass, normalized to that ejected by the eruption, for cases S_{200} (solid black line) and B_{200} (dashed blue line). Panel b presents the fraction of kinetic energy from the SN explosion for cases S_{200} (solid black line) and B_{200} (dashed blue line). The difference in time intervals is due to one curve being truncated when the SN remnant extends beyond the computational domain boundaries, preventing further tracking of its evolution.

Figure 5.4: Same as Figure 5.1 but for case B_{10} , with snapshots at 0, 2, 8, and 12 years after the SN explosion.

Tenorio-Tagle et al., 2015; Jiménez et al., 2021).

The decrease in kinetic energy is the result of strong radiative cooling within the CSM shell. In particular, when gas and dust particles within the swept-up circumstellar material collide. As the medium loses energy through radiative cooling, it cools down and the shock wave weakens. This process has implications for the survival of the dust, since both radiative cooling and the destruction of dust grains occur at high temperatures.

As expected, dust destruction in a bipolar CSM occurs more efficiently, as can be seen in panel *b* of Fig. 5.3. As a result, within the time interval of 115 years post-explosion, almost all the dust ($\sim 98\%$) is destroyed.

Ultimately, for both cases S_{200} and B_{200} , the shell will keep expanding, and the destruction of the dust grains will persist, as it can be seen in the plots in Fig. 5.3 the dust mass appears to keep decreasing. However, subsequent follow-up at later

times cannot be performed, as the boundaries of the computational domain have been reached.

Case B_{10} – 10-year eruption-SN delay

The case S_{10} also considers an CSM created by the bipolar eruption (as in case B_{200}), but it only proceeds for 10 years before the SN explosion. Unlike cases S_{200} and B_{200} , for this scenario the material piled during the eruption creates a denser shell, reaching densities $> 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, mostly concentrated at equatorial latitudes.

From Fig. 5.4 it can be seen that the shock interaction with the CSM shell appears at $t = 2$ years post-explosion in the equator, while the collision with the poles occurs at $t = 8$ years. Figure 5.5 shows the evolution of the dust fraction in panel *a* and the kinetic energy post-explosion in panel *b*. It is evident that the decreasing behavior in the kinetic energy is comparable with case B_{200} , since it decays rapidly once the shock wave interacts with the equator of the shell and causes it to weaken. The same occurs with the dust fraction. However, as observed in the bottom panel of Figure 5.4, the dust density is highly concentrated in the shell. Consequently, the results show that due to the weakening of the SN shock wave and the high shell densities, a larger fraction of dust survives. At time $t = 8$ years post-explosion, only a dust fraction of $\sim 30\%$ ($0.075 M_{\odot}$) is destroyed. Subsequently, as the shell continues to expand until $t = 12$ years, reaching the computational domain boundaries, the curve appears to remain stable, suggesting that potentially the dust grains prevail longer due to the fact that most of the energy has been radiated away.

Thus, the results suggest that the delay time between eruptive episodes and the subsequent SN explosion, is fundamental for the survival of dust grains created by such events.

Figure 5.5: Same as Figure 5.3, but for case B_{10} .

Model limitations

This section lists some of the limitations of the model implemented in the hydrodynamical simulations in this work.

- The model is based on the optically thin approach, overlooking cases where the optically thick regime becomes important.
- The simulations consider only thermal sputtering as the mechanism for dust destruction, neglecting potentially significant contributions from other destruction processes, due to constraints within the FLASH code.
- The simulations do not account for radiative transfer, magnetic fields, turbulence, and gravity. Although the last three may not be relevant for the current study.
- The model assumes a constant metallicity, not accounting for potential variations that could be significant in real astrophysical scenarios.
- The chosen resolution may not adequately capture the details of the dust injected by the eruption in cases where a larger computational domain is considered, possibly affecting the accuracy of the dust mass within the simulations.
- Finally, the model does not follow the formation of new dust particles, particularly in the post-shock CSM region.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

Three-dimensional hydrodynamical simulations of the evolution of a supernova (SN) remnant within a circumstellar material shell created by a stellar eruption were performed. The aim of this thesis was to study the impact that the SN explosion has on the dust grains formed after the eruption. The hydrodynamics involved includes the modeling of stellar winds, stellar eruptions, and a supernovae (SNe) explosions.

Various scenarios were examined based on the shape of the circumstellar medium (CSM) created by the eruption and the time elapsed prior to the SN explosion. Geometries featuring both spherical and bipolar CSM structures, resembling the configuration seen in the Homunculus Nebula, were under consideration.

The main conclusions obtained are discussed below.

The 3-D hydrodynamical modeling techniques applied in this work let us to simulate complex scenarios, since the FLASH code allows the implementation of several modules. In particular, the CINDER module is a novel tool that allows to calculate, on-the-fly, the radiative cooling induced by gas-grain collisions and thermal sputtering of dust grains. In this way, it is possible to follow the evolution of the dust mass injected by the source over time, which is appropriate to address the case of study in this work.

It is noteworthy that, to the best of my knowledge, this represents the first instance in which the survival of dust grains following stellar eruptions, in relation to an eventual SN explosion, has been modeled through the integrated hydrodynamical simulation of a stellar wind, a stellar eruption, and the subsequent SN explosion.

In order to properly characterize the physical properties of the stellar eruption, I

modified the WIND module in the FLASH code to include the first three-dimensional implementation of the bipolar morphology of the shell by introducing a function in the velocity field. Furthermore, I proposed an adapted version of the TM99 and (Tang & Chevalier, 2017) approach to describe the evolution of the bipolar shell, consistent with the features observed in the Homunculus Nebula.

By exploring various scenarios, we have the opportunity to compare different cases to determine where the dust has a greater chance of surviving and where its destruction is more effective. The results suggest that, with a 200-year eruption-SN time gap, only ~ 25 per cent of the dust remains 250 years after the SN explosion in the spherical case, while in the bipolar case, only 2 per cent remains after 115 years. However, as the shock wave progresses, leading to a continued decrease in the dust mass fraction, it is expected that eventually, all the remaining dust will be destroyed. On the other hand, in a 10-year eruption-supernova time separation, dust grains have a greater possibility of surviving for a longer time, since 12 years after the supernova explosion, the fraction of the surviving dust mass converges in about 70 per cent.

These results also show that the different geometric configurations of the CSM influence both the evolution of both the shell and the SN remnant, and the ability of the shock wave to destroy the dust.

As the SN shock wave gradually loses a fraction of its initial energy through the process of radiative cooling, its weakening becomes increasingly evident at later times. The phenomenon of interacting SNe holds significant implications for the preservation of environmental dust, as the attenuated shock wave may have a reduced impact on the surrounding dust particles, influencing their potential survival and distribution within the interstellar medium.

Future work

In the context of this work, the optically-thin approach is a critical consideration. Here, gas efficiently cools down because radiation can escape with minimal interaction with the medium. This regime is characterized by densities reaching values $\leq 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (Hartwig et al., 2015).

The results of the simulations show that the shell created by the eruption can reach densities on the order of 10^9 cm^{-3} , approaching the boundaries of the optically thick regime. This can lead to important implications for cooling, since the probability of escape of photons decreases drastically.

To enhance the accuracy of radiative cooling approximations, it is planned to account for the escape fraction of photons, particularly as it approaches this limit.

On the other hand, dust destruction studies are research efforts focused on understanding the processes and mechanisms that lead to the destruction of dust grains in several astrophysical environments. In particular, the study of rotational disruption by radiative torques and their effects on dust is an active area of research in astrophysics, hence it would be of great interest to study the impact of this destruction mechanism on the dust produced in stellar eruptions, such as the case of the bipolar shell of η Carinae.

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